

EBFMC25-OP-43 · Acute Viral Myositis Developed During Influenza B Infection and Incidental Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) Syndrome: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Acute viral myositis is common in children presenting with difficulty walking and is most frequently seen during viral infections such as influenza (Majava et al., 2024). We present a patient who was admitted with acute viral myositis and was incidentally diagnosed with Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome during his clinical evaluation.

Case Presentation: A 10-year-old male patient presented with complaints of fever, headache, sore throat, runny nose, and pain in the knees and legs (Arrab et al., 2024). The patient had no significant medical history, and the family history was notable for the early death of the father at 26 years of age. Physical examination revealed normal vital signs, hyperemia in the oropharynx, and preserved deep tendon reflexes (DTR). Other physical and neurological examination findings were normal. Acute rheumatic fever was considered in the differential diagnosis due to joint pain, and an electrocardiogram (ECG) was performed. The ECG revealed delta waves, consistent with Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The patient's respiratory viral panel tested positive for Influenza B. Laboratory findings showed a significantly elevated creatine kinase level of 11,645 U/L, with normal hemogram parameters, sedimentation rate of 24 mm/h, ASO level of 204 IU/mL, and CRP of 3.6 mg/L. The patient was hospitalized for observation, with the preliminary diagnoses of acute viral myositis and WPW syndrome. He received supportive care and hydration. During follow-up, creatine kinase levels decreased to the normal range. Pediatric cardiology evaluated the patient for WPW syndrome, and ablation was planned.

Discussion: Acute viral myositis is a common condition in children, often associated with viral infections such as influenza. While its clinical presentation is well-known, the association with Wolff-Parkinson-White (WPW) syndrome has not been reported in the literature. In this case, the incidental discovery of WPW syndrome during the diagnostic process for acute myositis highlights the importance of thorough clinical evaluation. The importance of such evaluations becomes even more pronounced when cardiac-involving diseases such as acute rheumatic fever are considered in the differential diagnosis. This case contributes to the understanding of the rare coexistence of these two conditions and emphasizes the need for careful consideration of all potential diagnoses in pediatric patients presenting with viral myositis.

Conclusion: This case emphasizes the importance of comprehensive diagnostic evaluation in pediatric patients, particularly when symptoms overlap with multiple conditions. Further research is warranted to investigate potential links between viral myositis and congenital arrhythmias such as WPW syndrome.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Acute viral myositis, influenza B, wolff-parkinson-white syndrome (WPW)

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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